

JURISPRUDENCE

ENCOURAGING BICYCLE MOVEMENT IN GEORGIA BASED ON THE EXAMPLE OF EUROPEAN COUNTRIES

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Abstract

In various countries around the modern world, transportation is one of the primary sources of greenhouse gas emissions. This sector negatively impacts the quality of life in urban areas, as it pollutes the air, causes unwanted noise, and exerts harmful effects on soil layers. Ultimately, this leads to land degradation, making it unusable for agricultural and other activities.

Excessive traffic, congestion, and road accidents are directly linked to human health, posing a significant threat to the normal existence of humanity. In many countries, this situation causes public dissatisfaction, which is often expressed through various forms of protest. In major cities and global metropolises, there is a continuous, dynamic process of modernizing the transportation sector based on rapid, planned, and contemporary technologies, while also incorporating global approaches and innovations. A key component of ongoing urban planning projects is the implementation of large-scale, diverse infrastructure mobility, including the strategy for accommodating bicycle traffic and establishing cycling facilities. Bicycle use and the development of cycling systems occupy an essential place among the core components of city master plans.

The resolution of these issues is directly related to governance structures that establish the necessary conditions for infrastructure development and the complete arrangement of safe bicycle lanes.

Using Georgia as an example, it can be noted that for the first time in the Caucasus, and even on an Asian scale, the "Bicycle Policy Audit" (BYPAD) methodology was applied in the development of Batumi's general plan. As for the situation in Tbilisi, it can be said that in terms of bicycle infrastructure development, bike lanes were established for the first time in the city's history in recent years, which should be considered one of the successful outcomes of the transportation reform. In the case of Georgia, it can be noted that the city of Batumi, during the development of its master plan, became the first in the Caucasus and across Asia to apply the methodology of the "Bicycle Policy Audit" (BYPAD). As for the situation in Tbilisi, in recent years, for the first time in the city's history, bicycle lanes have been established, which should be considered one of the successful outcomes of transportation reform.

Using qualitative research methods, this article examines the ways leading European countries promote bicycle use, including the implementation of state policies, the provision of appropriate legislative frameworks, the development of cycling infrastructure, and safety measures, as well as public awareness campaigns. The study analyzes the current situation in Georgia, ongoing legislative and educational initiatives, and infrastructure projects, identifying future activities planned to encourage cycling in the country.

Keywords: Bicycle, bicycle lane, cycling infrastructure, cycling sector, traffic, quality of life, air pollution.

Introduction

The subject of this research is a highly popular and relevant issue in the modern world, both by its nature and significance, as well as due to its increasing prioritization. A historical overview of sources allows us to discuss the foundational reasons behind the emergence of the bicycle lane system, which is tied to the invention of the bicycle.

"In 1790, the first bicycle, invented in France, resembled a two-wheeled wooden horse without pedals or a steering mechanism. In 1817, in Germany, a guiding mechanism for movement was added. By 1861, pedals appeared on bicycles in France. In 1870, the first large-front-wheeled bicycle was created in Britain. Finally, in 1903, the first cycling race, the Tour de France, was held."

The word "bicycle" originates from the French word "vélocipède," which means "fast foot." It refers to a two-wheeled mechanical vehicle (though there are also one-, three-, and four-wheeled modifications). It is

operated by pedaling, and speed is regulated through the use of these pedals.

In the routine rhythm of society's daily life, the bicycle has held a significant place for centuries due to its functional utility. For instance:

In London and Tallinn, emergency medical personnel use bicycles for transportation;

During the Anglo-Boer War (1899-1902), both sides (Great Britain and the South African Republics) successfully used bicycles for reconnaissance and communication;

During World War I, bicycles were used for reconnaissance, communication, and transporting the wounded;

In 1937, Japan actively used bicycles during its invasion of China, and again in 1941 during its invasion of Singapore;

In the Wehrmacht, all reconnaissance battalions of infantry divisions included cyclist units;

During World War II, folding bicycles were part of the equipment used in Allied operations, particularly by paratroopers;

During the Vietnam War, guerrilla fighters used bicycles for transporting goods;

Cyclist units existed in the armed forces of Sweden and Switzerland until the early 2000s;

In Great Britain, Germany, Hungary, and in the postal services of many countries, bicycles remain an irreplaceable means of transportation.

Despite the boom in automobile transportation in various European countries, the bicycle has retained its special significance, leading to the development of cycling infrastructure to meet existing needs. The networks of bicycle lanes created as part of transportation reforms are noteworthy. Active efforts are underway to develop and implement safety regulations and standards for cycling lanes. Additionally, research is being conducted to assess the impact of bicycle lanes in reducing transport-related pollution, with the aim of creating a sustainable and viable environment.

During the existence of the Soviet Union, cycling as a form of road transport was not developed in the cities of Georgia, which was part of this totalitarian state.

It is worth noting that in many highly developed European countries, such as the Netherlands, Denmark, Germany, and France, the bicycle has long been and continues to be one of the most popular means of transportation for the population. Furthermore, these countries continuously update their efforts to further popularize cycling as a mode of transport.

Netherlands

Cycling became popular in the Netherlands at the beginning of the 1900s. The favorable landscape and compact cities made bicycles an ideal mode of transportation. Before World War II, cities in the Netherlands were known for their large number of cyclists, and the bicycle was the primary means of transportation. However, after World War II, as in many other Western countries, the use of automobiles increased in the Netherlands, and urban planning increasingly favored cars, leading to a decline in bicycle use. By the 1970s, the growing number of cars caused a sharp increase in traffic accidents, many of which involved cyclists. This provoked public outrage, and in response to the high number of child deaths in road accidents, the movement "Stop de Kindermoord" ("Stop the Child Murder") emerged, calling for safer streets and better cycling infrastructure in the country (Fact sheet Cycling infrastructure, 2024). The 1973 oil crisis highlighted the vulnerability of a car-dependent society and sparked interest in alternative transportation methods, including cycling (Decisio, 2016). In response to public pressure and the oil crisis, the Dutch government began investing in the development of cycling infrastructure, and policies promoting cycling and public transportation became a priority over private transport.

Cities started building extensive networks of segregated bike lanes, making cycling safer and more attractive. Amsterdam and other large cities became models of urban cycling infrastructure (Fiets van de zaak, 2020). In the Netherlands, urban planning integrates bicycles into the broader transport system, with

dedicated bike lanes, parking facilities, and traffic signals specifically designed for cyclists.

Over the decades, cycling has become part of Dutch culture. It is included in school curriculums, and various campaigns promote the health, environmental, and social benefits of cycling. The country continues to invest in cycling infrastructure, maintaining bike lanes and expanding parking facilities. Innovations such as smart traffic lights that prioritize cyclists and the development of "bicycle highways" (long-distance, high-capacity bike routes) reflect the Netherlands' ongoing commitment to cycling. Overall, the approach to cycling infrastructure and policy in the Netherlands has created one of the most cyclist-friendly environments in the world, promoting bicycles as a sustainable and safe mode of transport and serving as a model for other countries.

In the Netherlands, bicycle purchases are often subsidized through various programs and incentives aimed at promoting bicycles as a sustainable and safe means of transport. For example, the tax-free bicycle scheme, known as the Dutch "fiets van de zaak" scheme, allows employers to provide bicycles free of charge to employees, who can use them for commuting and personal use. This scheme often includes electric bicycles and even high-end models. Many employers offer bicycle leasing programs, where employees can rent bicycles at discounted rates through salary deductions, making high-quality bicycles more accessible (Fiets van de zaak, 2020).

At the same time, government subsidies and incentives, along with local government initiatives, play a crucial role. Some municipalities offer subsidies or grants for purchasing bicycles, particularly electric bikes, to encourage residents to switch from cars to bicycles. These programs vary by region and often aim to reduce traffic congestion and improve air quality. Certain subsidies may be available for specific groups, such as students, low-income families, or the elderly, making bicycles more affordable. Some schemes provide discounts on new bicycles when trading in old ones to purchase a newer model (Fact sheet Cycling infrastructure, 2024).

Together, these initiatives create a supportive environment for cycling, making it an attractive and financially viable option for residents of the country.

Denmark

The development of appropriate infrastructure for cyclists in Denmark began at the dawn of the 20th century. The bicycle gained popularity, leading to the creation of the first dedicated bike lanes in the capital city of Copenhagen in the 1910s and 1920s. The growth in the number of cyclists prompted city planners to start designing bicycle infrastructure. Copenhagen's first dedicated bike lane was opened in 1934. Despite a shift toward a more car-oriented society in the mid-20th century, the bicycle remained a popular mode of transportation, and improvements to cycling infrastructure continued (The Rise of Cycling in Denmark, 2024).

In Denmark, particularly in Copenhagen, the growth of cycling is supported by a combination of infrastructural, political, and cultural factors:

Extensive Cycling Infrastructure and Investment – The country invests significantly in the development of

high-quality cycling infrastructure. Denmark boasts a vast network of dedicated bike lanes, with Copenhagen alone having over 390 kilometers of bike lanes, many of which are segregated from car traffic. These include bridges and tunnels specifically for cyclists (City of Copenhagen, 2023).

Safety Measures – Bike lanes are designed with the safety of cyclists in mind. This includes specific traffic lights for cyclists, safe crossing points, well-designed intersections, and separate bike lanes to enhance safety and encourage more people to cycle (Andersen, 2021).

Cycling-Friendly Policies – The government prioritizes cycling as a mode of transport, giving cyclists the right of way in many situations, making cycling a preferred option on the roads (Cycling in Denmark: A Model for Sustainable Urban Mobility, 2024).

Bicycle Parking and Urban Planning – Denmark has numerous bicycle parking facilities, including large racks and secure parking areas at public venues. Urban planning also incorporates cycling into the city's design, ensuring that bicycles are the most convenient and efficient form of transportation for daily commutes (City of Copenhagen, 2023).

Public Awareness and Culture – Cycling is deeply ingrained in Danish culture. Many people choose to cycle daily, whether for leisure or commuting to work (Cycling in Denmark: A Model for Sustainable Urban Mobility, 2024).

Education and Campaigns – The government and various organizations run regular educational campaigns to raise public awareness, encouraging cycling and teaching citizens about its benefits. Schools often include cycling education in their curriculum, emphasizing health, environmental, and financial advantages (Andersen, 2021).

Economic Incentives – Financial incentives and subsidies are available for purchasing bicycles, especially electric bikes. There are also tax benefits for companies that promote cycling among employees (City of Copenhagen, 2023).

Integration with Public Transport – There is seamless integration between cycling and public transport, with bicycle parking facilities at train and bus stations and the ability to bring bicycles onto trains (Cycling in Denmark: A Model for Sustainable Urban Mobility, 2024).

Cycling Events and Initiatives – Denmark organizes and supports various cycling events, such as "Bike to Work Day." During rush hour, cycling is often faster and more convenient than driving (Andersen, 2021).

Support for Innovation – Denmark encourages and supports technological and service innovations related to cycling, such as bike-sharing programs and mobile apps for cyclists (City of Copenhagen, 2023).

The Danish government actively promotes interest in cycling, and these combined measures create an environment where cycling is convenient, safe, and popular.

Federal Republic of Germany

The popularity of bicycles in Germany began to rise in the late 1800s. Early cycling clubs and volunteer groups formed, promoting the bicycle as a recreational

and transportation tool. In the 1920s and 1930s, Germany developed plans for building bicycle lanes, primarily in cities. Like many other countries, Germany saw an increase in motor vehicle use after World War II, which led to a decline in bicycle infrastructure and usage (Bicycle Planning and Policy in Germany, 2023). In the 1960s and 1970s, urban planning heavily favored cars, often at the expense of cyclists and pedestrians. The oil crisis of the 1970s highlighted the need for alternative modes of transportation, sparking renewed interest in the bicycle as an economical and environmentally friendly way to travel. Growing environmental awareness and public health campaigns in the 1980s and 1990s supported sustainable urban mobility, including cycling (Cycling in Germany: History and Future, 2022). By the end of the 20th century, both federal and local governments began investing in cycling infrastructure. Policies and funding were directed towards building and improving bicycle lanes and related facilities. Many cities and regions developed comprehensive cycling plans. For example, cities like Berlin, Hamburg, and Munich expanded their networks of bicycle lanes and bike-friendly streets (Fahrradinfrastruktur in Deutschland, 2020). Various campaigns and programs promote cycling, including initiatives that encourage commuting by bicycle and public awareness campaigns about the benefits of cycling.

In recent years, Germany has seen a sharp increase in people choosing to cycle, driven by factors such as awareness of climate change and the rise of electric bicycles. Continued investments in cycling infrastructure have followed. Examples include the construction of "Radschnellwege" (bicycle highways) to promote long-distance cycling, as well as the development of bike-sharing programs in many cities (Cycling in Germany: History and Future, 2022). Measures have also been taken to integrate bicycles into the public transport system, including providing bike parking at train stations and allowing bicycles on public transit. Improvements in road safety measures for cyclists, such as better lighting, road signs, and traffic-calming devices, have also been implemented.

At the same time, cycling has become an integral part of urban culture in many German cities. It is seen as a practical and efficient mode of transportation for commuting, shopping, and recreation. Schools and community programs often include training on safe cycling for children and adolescents.

Notably, the COVID-19 pandemic led to a significant increase in cycling in Germany, as people sought socially distanced modes of transport. Temporary bike lanes were introduced in many cities, with some becoming permanent due to their popularity (Cycling in Germany: History and Future, 2022).

Overall, Germany's approach to the development of cycling is characterized by growing recognition of the bicycle's benefits for urban mobility, health, and the environment. The country continues to invest in and promote cycling as a key component of sustainable transportation.

France

Cycling gained popularity in France in the late 1800s, becoming fashionable both as a recreational activity and a means of transportation. Cycling clubs and events, such as the "Tour de France" (founded in 1903), helped to popularize the cycling culture. France followed a similar path to other European countries in developing cycling infrastructure and promoting cycling as a means of transport (Papon, 2021). Under the leadership of Paris Mayor Anne Hidalgo, Paris has become a model for urban cycling. The city has significantly expanded its cycling infrastructure, including protected bike lanes, bike-sharing applications (like "Vélib"), and car-free zones. The introduction of the "Vélib" bike-sharing app in 2007 was a major step forward in promoting cycling. This system has since been expanded to other cities in France (Vélib' Bike-Sharing Program, 2023).

Additionally, some regions have developed "voies vertes" (greenways) and "véloroutes" (cycling routes) to promote long-distance cycling, connecting rural areas and villages (Papon, 2021). Cycling is increasingly popular for commuting, leisure, and tourism. The French government supports cycling through campaigns and events like "Semaine du vélo" (Bike Week), and schools and community programs often include training for children and adolescents on safe cycling (La Semaine du vélo: Promouvoir le cyclisme pour tous, 2022).

France continues to invest in cycling infrastructure, with plans for further expansion of bike lanes and integration with public transport. The French government has set ambitious goals to promote cycling, including subsidies for purchasing bicycles (particularly e-bikes), tax benefits for cyclists, and significant funding for cycling projects. Paris, in particular, has launched several phases of the "Plan Vélo," aiming to become 100% bike-friendly by 2026, with extensive cycling networks and infrastructure improvements. Overall, France's approach to cycling development reflects a growing recognition of the benefits of cycling for urban development, health, and the environment (Making Paris Bike-Friendly by 2026, 2023).

Georgia

Following the restoration of state independence, Georgian legislation, particularly the law initially passed by the Parliament of Georgia on May 28, 1999, titled "On Road Traffic Safety" (Law of Georgia, www.matsne.gov.ge, 1999), and currently the "Law on Road Traffic," which came into effect on March 1, 2014, established the legal foundations for organizing road traffic and ensuring traffic safety in Georgia. This law outlines the primary directions of state policy in road traffic safety, the responsibilities of state authorities, traffic rules and conditions, road signs, markings, and the rights and obligations of road users, among other aspects (Law of Georgia, www.matsne.gov.ge, 2013).

At the legislative level, terms such as bicycle, bicycle path (bike lane), and bicycle lane have been defined. Specifically, according to the aforementioned law:

A bicycle is a vehicle with at least two wheels that is powered solely by the muscular energy of the person riding it, specifically through pedals or handles. This term does not include wheelchairs. Electric bicycles are also equated to bicycles.

A bicycle path (bike lane) is a road or part of a road designated for bicycle movement, marked with the appropriate road signs, and separated from other parts of the road or its other elements by design.

A bicycle lane is a lane on the roadway designated for bicycle traffic. This lane is separated from the rest of the roadway by longitudinal road markings (Law of Georgia, www.matsne.gov.ge, 2013).

Furthermore, the term "road" in the law can encompass bicycle lanes. Additionally, this legislative act established the basic principles and specific rules for cycling on bike lanes or bicycle lanes by road users, laying the groundwork for the promotion and future development of cycling in Georgia.

The annex (Annex №1 on Road Signs) of the law defines the following:

Warning road sign 1.25: "Bicycle Lane Crossing" – this sign warns drivers about approaching a crossing point for a bicycle lane marked by sign 4.4.

These legislative measures aim to promote cycling in Georgia by providing a legal framework for its development and integration into the country's traffic system.

1.25

ველობლივის

გადაკვეთა

Prohibitory road sign 3.9: "Bicycle Traffic Prohibited" – This sign prohibits the movement of bicycles and mopeds in the designated area.

3.9

ველოსიპედით
მძრაობა აკრძალულია

Directional road sign 4.4: "Bicycle Path" – This sign indicates a path specifically designated for bicycle traffic, which is structurally separated from other parts

of the road or its elements. The 4.4 sign is placed primarily at the start of the bicycle path and is repeated after each road crossing.

4.4

ველობილიკო

The law's Annex №2 (Road Markings) established horizontal marking 1.15, which indicates the location where a bicycle lane intersects with the roadway. This marking helps both cyclists and other road users to identify the crossing point, improving safety and road navigation.

This provision ensures better organization of traffic, making the roads safer and more efficient for all users. (Law of Georgia, www.matsne.gov.ge, 2013)

1.15

In accordance with the aforementioned legislative amendment, changes were made to Article 125 of the Administrative Offenses Code of Georgia, adding part 13, which states that the movement, stopping, or parking of any vehicle other than a bicycle (with exceptions permitted by Georgian law) on a bicycle path or bicycle lane will result in a fine of 100 GEL. Additionally, according to note 11 of the same article, in cases where the offense specified in part 13 is committed, the parked or stopped vehicle may be immediately towed to a special secured parking lot. The vehicle will be returned to its owner/holder upon the presentation of documents proving payment of the towing and storage fees, the vehicle's registration certificate or power of attorney, a document proving the right to use the vehicle as per Georgian law, and an identity document.

The representative body of the municipality is authorized to determine the fees for towing and storing vehicles in a special secured parking lot in cases of administrative offenses under the municipality's jurisdiction. (Law of Georgia, www.matsne.gov.ge, 2019).

Based on the above changes in the Administrative Offenses Code of Georgia, a change was made to the decision of the Tbilisi Municipal Assembly from December 27, 2016, №33-99, titled "On Approving the Rules for Regulating Parking of Vehicles within the Administrative Boundaries of the City of Tbilisi and on Determining the Fees for Towing and Storing Vehicles in a Special Secured Parking Lot, and for Wheel Clamping." This decision established the fees for towing and storing vehicles in a special secured parking lot in cases of administrative offenses (Tbilisi Municipal Assembly Decision, 2016).

Comprehensive research conducted in 2023 revealed the following transportation patterns within the administrative boundaries of Georgia's capital: 39.1% of people use public transport (including 16.4% using M2 category buses (minibuses), 15.3% using M3 category buses (large and medium-capacity buses), and 7.4% using underground electric transport (metro)); 27.7% use private cars; 26.9% are pedestrians; 2.8% use "A" category light vehicles (taxis, M1 category); 1.3% use other means of transport; and only 0.1%-0.1% use bicycles or two-wheeled electric scooters (Tbilisi Transport Plan 2023-2043).

In recent years, approximately 35 kilometers of bicycle lanes have been constructed in Tbilisi, marking a significant beginning in the process of creating a network of bike lanes. Every year, more and more cyclists appear on the streets of Tbilisi, although the network is still not extensive enough to provide a truly safe environment for cycling throughout the city (Tbilisi Transport Plan 2023-2043).

Other Issues Related to Cycling

Several challenges hinder the growth and safety of cycling in Tbilisi:

Limited Bicycle Routes: There are very few routes with dedicated bicycle lanes. **Lack of Connectivity:** Bicycle routes are not interconnected, restricting the distances and areas where cyclists can safely travel. **Inadequate Bicycle Infrastructure:** Bicycle infrastructure, particularly at intersections, is not always well-protected, visible, or clearly marked, creating potential conflicts between different road users. **High Speed Limits:** The high speed limits for vehicles and lack of speed control in local streets create hazardous conditions for cyclists. **Limited Bicycle Parking:** There is a shortage of bicycle parking facilities, except for a few bike stations along main corridors and in commercial areas. Considering these challenges, the Tbilisi City Hall developed the 2023-2043 Long-Term Transport Plan – Sustainable Urban Mobility Strategy, which aims to prioritize accessibility, sustainability, and inclusivity, all of which are vital for creating a vibrant urban environment. The plan envisions that by 2043, the modal share of transportation in the city will be characterized as follows: 43% of the population will use public transportation (M2 category buses (minibuses), M3 category buses (large and medium-capacity buses), and underground electric transport (metro)); 27% will be pedestrians; 20% will use private cars; 8% will cycle; and 2% will use "A" category light vehicles (taxis, M1 category).

When comparing the 2043 projections with the 2023 data, it becomes evident that a sharp increase in cycling is expected. To achieve this, the action plan includes legislative and institutional changes, improvements to urban living quality, parking management, and road safety. To make cycling safer, more attractive, and reliable, the plan includes a wide range of programs aimed at creating safe cycling infrastructure and raising awareness about cycling. It also focuses on expanding the availability of shared bicycles, with a particular focus on increasing the number of bicycle routes within the capital's administrative boundaries. In the long

term, the bicycle network is projected to expand to a total of 325 kilometers (Tbilisi Transport Plan 2023-2043).

The 20-year strategy also includes a 5-year Action Plan for 2024-2028, which, among other large-scale projects, involves redesigning four of the eleven bridges over the Mtkvari River in Tbilisi — Metekhi Bridge, Saarbrucken/Dry Bridge, Galaktion Bridge, and Baratashvili Bridge (which are mainly used for automobile traffic) — to make them safer and more attractive for pedestrians and cyclists. Tbilisi's weather is ideal for cycling most of the year, but given that the city is large and the current 35 kilometers of bike lanes cover only a small portion of it, the network is insufficient for ensuring a truly safe cycling environment. Moreover, these lanes are not always continuous and do not form a connected network. Cycling on streets without bike lanes can be extremely dangerous.

Thus, the focus is on completing Tbilisi's cycling network with a dual strategy: creating connected, safe, and attractive bicycle routes. With the assistance of the German Development Agency (GIZ), an additional 30 kilometers of bike routes will be added, and in the long term, the network will reach 325 kilometers. In the short term, high-quality bike lanes will be constructed along major transport corridors, the riverbanks, and across the Vake and Saburtalo districts. By 2022, 20 kilometers of bike routes had already been built in Tbilisi, and the goal is to create fully segregated bike lanes separated from motor traffic for safety and comfort. In the short term, buffer bike lanes will be constructed, and in the future, for optimal safety, bike lanes will be elevated to sidewalk level using concrete.

Along with the general bike network, Tbilisi also plans to create "bike-friendly districts" or "Velo-Districts". These are areas where independent cycling networks allow safe travel to any part of the district. A pilot Velo-District will be implemented in the Marjanishvili district, with a second possible Velo-District planned for Saburtalo. Both strategies will include additional infrastructure such as high-quality lighting, road signs for navigation, dedicated traffic lights giving priority to cyclists, and new crossings over rivers and railways. Additionally, bike parking will be installed along the network, near major bus and metro stations, and bicycle repair service centers will be established.

It is important to note that the general network and Velo-Districts are only the first steps toward a broader city-wide cycling network. The long-term vision for Tbilisi is to design all urban streets to be safe for cyclists. Thus, cyclist safety will be considered in the redesign of every street.

Conclusion

The analysis presented in this paper leads to the conclusion that the implementation and development of a comprehensive bicycle lane system is essential when designing transport infrastructure. Bicycle lanes provide a safe means of transportation and are also ecologically significant, directly impacting public health. It is generally recommended that bicycle lanes be constructed along high-speed and inner-city roads, and

they must be physically separated from both motor vehicle traffic and pedestrian pathways.

In major cities of developed countries with advanced economies, modern mobile cycling infrastructures have been created, utilizing contemporary technologies. These systems enable residents to use bicycles year-round. In the context of public health and environmental protection, as well as in various specialized fields, research is conducted on the development of the cycling sector, both in academic and professional circles. These studies and their qualified recommendations further demonstrate the priority and necessity of the subject. Research indicates that air pollution in Georgia is primarily caused by vehicle emissions, which negatively affect both human health and the environment.

To improve this situation, Georgia's legislative and executive bodies have been actively implementing various measures, both by adopting legislative and regulatory acts and ensuring their enforcement. Examples include the Law on Road Traffic, amendments to the Administrative Code, regulatory documents passed by municipal councils, and their enforcement as outlined in this paper. These efforts demonstrate the country's commitment to improving transportation safety and infrastructure.

Public awareness regarding cycling and related infrastructure must be raised to foster a positive attitude towards this system. International organizations have also taken special approaches to this research topic. Regular meetings are held under the auspices of the United Nations and the WHO's Pan-European Programme on Transport, Health, and Environment, where various positions are expressed. However, rational decisions are ultimately made, with a consensus that "to promote walking and cycling in cities, municipalities should improve pedestrian and cycling infrastructure and raise public awareness about a healthy lifestyle."

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